

COLEÇÃO histórias das história. São Paulo: Brasil, 2016.

BRAZ, Júlio Emílio. **Um encontro com a liberdade** [An encounter with freedom]. Illustration by Roberto Weigand. São Paulo, 2016. 59 p.

MANUEL FILHO. **Uma história de ouro e sangue** [A story of gold and blood]. Illustration by Daniel Araújo. São Paulo: Brasil, 2016. 115 p.

ROZEN, Beti; HAYS, Peter. **Dois continentes, quatro gerações** [Two continents, four generations]. Illustration by Julia Back. São Paulo: Brasil, 2016. 146 p.

REVIEW¹

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Histórias da História is a collection that intends to provoke the reader to rescue in History the memory of moments that cannot be forgotten. To make the encounter with the past more enjoyable, we have Literature as a travel companion. With each report read, a period is to be unveiled. In the work *Dois continentes, quatro gerações* the character Louis comes across his grandfather's Poland and the immigration process of the family to Brazil. In the book *Um encontro com a liberdade*, the theme of the slavery period is addressed in the story of the character Gabriel. In *Uma história de ouro e sangue*, the author tells the story of São Paulo, reporting on the 1932 Constitutionalist Revolution. The book presents Afonsinho and his initiation in the world of work, as an office boy in the heart of the city of São Paulo. These are fictions that address debates that are always necessary.

Keywords: Memory. Immigration. Culture.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2017 Bologna. Books published in 2016 and reviewed in 2017. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva.

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